

ISic1158

I.Sicily inscription 1158

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (white)

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Found at Termini Imerese

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 133

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 20 cm

Width 15.5 cm

Depth 2.8 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]λία
2. [Σπ]αρτεΐνα
3. [Λι]λυβαΐτις
4. [ἔζη]σεν ἔτη
5. κβ

Apparatus

Text after IGTermini (Brugnone)

Kaibel, Cagnat, Manganaro: [Αύρη]λία

Manganaro: [Κου]αρτεΐνα

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284964

EDCS 39102314

PHI 140643

PHI 331801

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1158. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4351661>